

The Journalist Survey

This is a System Usability Survey dedicated to our game called "The Journalist" for EduGames Project. Please pick the numbers according to how much you agree to each statement. Feel free to talk about the statement and tell us more.

* Indicates required question

1. Age?

2. Gender?

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

3. I think that I would like to play this game frequently. *

(Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

4. Tell us more...

5. I found the game unnecessarily complex. *
- (Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

6. Tell us more...

7. I thought the game reflected the disinformation that we see in our daily life well. *
- (Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

8. Tell us more...

9. I thought the game was too didactic *
(Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

10. Tell us more...

11. I thought the game was both entertaining and educational. *
(Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

12. Tell us more...

13. I thought the game could not reflect the idea of construction of truth through document analysis. *

(Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

14. Tell us more...

15. I would imagine that most people would learn to play this game very quickly. *

(Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

16. Tell us more...

17. This game would not help the players to find reliable sources. *
- (Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

18. Tell us more...

19. I would play this game if new updates come. *
- (Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

20. Tell us more...

21. I thought the game didn't show how easy to mislead public on certain topics. *
- (Strongly disagree: 1 Disagree: 2 Neutral: 3 Agree: 4 Strongly Agree: 5)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

22. Tell us more...

Thank you so much for taking a part in this research and playing our game.

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

